

The Effects of Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour: (A conceptual framework).

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Abstract

In recent times, organizations have been striving to achieve excellence in relation to the effectiveness and efficiency of employees. The behavior of individuals can help organizations to achieve this goal. It has been noted by several researchers that organizational citizenship behavior is a workplace behavior, which is optional because when individuals engage in this kind of behavior they voluntarily do more than is expected of them for the organization and this in turn increases their performance as well as that of the entire organization. It has been mentioned by many researchers that organizational commitment and organizational support are two factors that can significantly affect the sustainability of organizations as well as the organizational citizenship behavior while increasing the competitive advantage of the organization. Based on the fact organizations strive to support their employees as well as strengthen their commitment. In general, findings of past studies have argued that organizational citizenship behaviour is directly determined by organizational commitment and organizational support. By highlighting the effects of organizational support and organizational commitment on the organizational citizenship behaviour, the direct and indirect effects on employee performance are explained in this article.

Keywords: *Organizational Support, Organizational Commitment, Organizational Citizenship Behaviour.*

1. Introduction

Motivating and managing employees in an organization remains one of the major challenges faced by leaders in a highly competitive world. Thus, for the competitive advantage of an organization to be sustained, the effective management of human resources alongside their attitudes is crucial (Ibrahim, Ghani, & Embat, 2013). In this regard, job attitude is being considered by Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller (2012) as a crucial and central aspect of employee behaviour. They argue that job attitudes are very important because they have the potentials of predicting important behaviour. Thus, they suggest that there is need for the further integration of job attitudes with future research in order to explain employee behaviours under frameworks that are multidimensional. It is therefore important to note that the attitudes of human resources to their work is very important and that there are so many challenges associated to these attitudes including the inability of management to deal with such work related attitudes and how they affect the behaviour and performance of employees (Emami, Alizadeh, Nazari, & Darvishi, 2012).

Chiu, Huang, Cheng and Sun (2015), emphasized the importance of organizational support in the relationship between organization and employees; the manner in which work attitude and employee behaviours is affected by the relationship between employees and organization is explained using the social exchange theory. Most times social exchange theory, organization anthropomorphic thinking and reciprocal specification are used in perceived organizational support studies. A sense of obligation is given to the employees through reciprocal specification so that they can be able to give back to their organization. Thus, the performance, job satisfaction, organizational commitment as well as the role of external behaviour can be affected by perceived organizational support. Inconsistent results on the effect of organizational support on organizational citizenship behaviour has been identified in the literature. For instance, findings of a study conducted by Miao and Kim (2010) found that job satisfaction and OCB were positively and significantly affected by organizational support. However, the a meta-analysis on the outcomes of organizational support revealed that OCB is moderately affected by organizational support (Ahmed, Nawaz, Ali, & Islam, 2015). In contrast, Chan (2014) found a weak and negative relationship between organizational support and OCB. Due to this inconsistencies identified in the literature, further research on the factors influencing the difference in results on organizational support as a predicting factor of OCB is suggested by Ahmad and Omar (2015).

Organizational commitment has been identified as the most attitudinal predicting factor of OCB among other (ÜNÜVAR, 2006). Organizational citizenship behaviour can be enhanced by an organization if they are able to influence organizational commitment (Huang, You, & Tsai, 2012). Organizational commitment has been highlighted by many researchers as a significant determinant of OCB (Allen, Evans, & White, 2011; Olowookere, 2014; Premchandani & Sitlani, 2015; Rehan & Islam, 2013; Steyrer, Schiffinger, & Lang, 2008). Furthermore, the job satisfaction of employees as well as their willingness to be more involved in OCB can be increased through employee's commitment to an organization (Paulin, Ferguson, & Bergeron, 2006).

In contrast, so many other researchers have not been able to show evidence for the existence of a significant and positive relationship between organizational commitment and OCB (Chu, Lee, Hsu, & Chen, 2005; Tang & Ibrahim, 1998; Williams & Anderson, 1991). Despite the fact that numerous studies have been conducted to examine the relationship between organizational commitment and OCB, there is a scarcity of simultaneous and specific studies on the relationship between foci and dimensions of commitment and OCB (Duarte, 2015). In addition, Dehghani, Hayat, Kojuri, and Esmi (2015) suggested that further studies should be conducted to investigate the relationship between OCB and other variables such as organizational commitment have suggested it. Based on the recommendations given by other researchers, the inconsistencies in findings and scarcity of specific and simultaneous studies, this study will carry out to examine organizational commitment as a predicting factor of organizational citizenship behaviour.

Extra-role behaviours and in-role behaviours are the two main classifications of individual behaviours. Extra-role behaviours include behaviours like helping new colleagues, rendering assistance to colleagues with much work and promoting the organization (Dash & Pradhan, 2013). Researchers have defined OCB as behaviours that are voluntarily exhibited by employees; the performance of the individuals and that of the organization can be improved through this optional behaviour (Dash & Pradhan, 2013; Kevin, 2016; Rose, Miller, & Kacirek, 2016). OCB can affect individual performances in negative and positive ways (Dash & Pradhan, 2013). More so, the overall performance of the organization can be impacted by OCB which influences individual behaviours (Coldwell & Callaghan, 2014; Jain, Giga, & Cooper, 2011; Van Dooren, Bouckaert, & Halligan, 2015). Again, studies on work related attitudes and its relationship with OCB in other fields of study can benefit from growing interest in organizational citizenship behaviour (Jain et al., 2011). Some researchers have argued that the theoretical and practical aspect of OCB can provide insight on the significance of social connections within societies Bergeron, Ostroff, Schroeder, and Block (2014) and Rose (2016).

1. Theoretical Background

1.1 Organizational Support and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

Organizational support can be defined as the beliefs of the staff of an organization that it appreciates their efforts and prioritizes their welfare. (Eisenberger, Malone, & Presson, 2016). Hence, the opinions of the staff that their welfare is valued and their efforts are appreciated contains two meanings. The first one is the opinion that the organization recognizes their contributions. Secondly, the employees perception that their welfare is of priority to the organization.. (Ahmed & Nawaz, 2015). Individuals who have high organizational support will meet the requirements for validation, recognition and social identity, they expect that their outstanding performance and behaviour in the organization will be recognized (Eisenberger, Lynch, Aselage, & Rohdieck, 2004). Nevertheless, studies have shown that employees whose level organizational support is high believe the organization is concerned with their wellbeing, and as a reaction to this, they participate with Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (Eisenberger et al., 2016).

A lot of researchers have carried out practical tests on the connection between perceived organizational support and various employee attitudes. The results showed that the perceived organizational support positively influenced the staff's attitudes in terms of job satisfaction. (Ngo, Loi, Foley, Zheng, & Zhang 2013; Thompson,

& Phua, 2012), organizational citizenship behavior (Chen et al., 2015; Cheung, 2013; Chiang & Hsieh, 2012), engagement (e.g. Shantz, Alfes, Truss, & Soane, 2013) and turnover intentions (Bogler & Nir, 2012).

Organ and Ryan carried out a meta-analytic evaluation of 55 studies and the findings showed that leader supportiveness, justice and organizational commitment are important determinant factors of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. Draves (2004) evaluated the relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behaviour and Organizational Support considering factors like perceived work control, equity sensitivity, work locus of control, conscientiousness, as well as exchange ideology and believed obligation was a possible moderator. Findings from this research revealed that organizational support has a significant relationship with sense of obligation. Conscientiousness was related to both Organizational Citizenship Behaviour and sense of obligation. Conscientiousness also serves as a mediator between the sense of obligation and OCB. It also served as a mediator in the relationship between organizational support and sense of obligation. Sense of obligation was the major determinant factor of OCB and the mediator between organizational support and OCB.

A study of 199 employees of a large electronics and appliance sales organization in the North Eastern USA revealed that organizational support enhances extra performance (Chen & Chiu, 2009).

Results from study conducted by Stokes et al. (2013) for organizational support as mediator in the relationship between organizational stressors and OCB using call centre organizations in India as a case study showed that the relationship between organizational stressors and OCB was negative. A significant positive relationship between organizational support and OCB was found, and it was also confirmed that the relationship between organizational stressors and OCB is moderated by organizational support.

Muhammad (2014) carried out a study for organizational support and OCB using Kuwait as a case study with effective commitment as a moderator. His findings revealed that, organizational support has a positive relationship with affective organizational commitment, and affective organizational commitment moderates the connection between organizational support and OCB. A study conducted by Chan (2014) in ZUN UTARA industry also explored the relationship between organizational support, work engagement, and OCB. Findings from the research showed that work engagement has a strong relationship with OCB, and organizational support has weak relationship with OCB. More so, of these two independent variables, work engagement is the major contributor to OCB.

Ahmed and Nawaz (2015) also conducted a study on the predicting factors and outcomes of organizational support. A survey showed that organizational support is mainly affect by growth opportunities as well as support from colleagues and supervisor. After thoroughly looking at these results, it is obvious that organizational support's level of influence on the employees' level of contentment at work is high compared to its impact on OCB and turnover intentions, which is neutral.

1.2 Organizational Commitment and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour

In the past decade, the concept of organizational commitment has become a prominent topic in the field of organizational psychology and organizational behaviour. (ÜNÜVAR, 2006).

In alignment to this fact, Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, and Topolnytsky (2002) confirmed that many empirical studies on the predicting factors and outcomes of organizational commitment have been carried out. The growth of interest in the organizational commitment literature is due to the fact that the concept plays a major role in the employee's psychological conditions. This is due to the fact that employees with high organizational commitment are believed to exhibit a more positive behaviour at work such as enhanced job performance, and OCB, thereby contributing to the growth of the organization (Albdour & Altarawneh, 2014).

The relative strength of the relationship between an individual and an organization often characterized by a strong belief in and the acceptance of the organization's norms and goals, strong drive to continue being a member of the organization and the willingness to go extra miles for the organization is regarded as organizational commitment (Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 2013). According to this definition, there are three

major elements associated with organizational commitment: (1) strong belief in and acceptance of the norms and goals of the organization; (2) strong drive to do more extra work for the organization; and (3) passion to remain a member of the organization desire to continue membership in the organization” (Mowday et al., 2013).

It is obvious that an employee who has strong affective commitment will willingly accept the goals of the organization, will be happier to remain an employee of the organization and to continue working for the organization (Mowday et al., 2013). On the other hand, an employee will not have the drive to work extra for an organization neither will he/she want to continue being a member of the organization when he/she no longer feels emotionally attached to the organization (Mohsan, Nawaz, Khan, Shaukat, & Aslam, 2011).

However, the OCB of employees can be improved if organizations are able to influence the job satisfaction of employees, ethical climate of the organization, and organizational commitment Huang et al. (2012). The affective commitment, normative commitment, satisfaction with co-workers and rules and regulations climate can be promoted by the management of organizations in order to increase employees OCB while preventing the development of a climate that reduces it (Huang et al. 2012).

LePine, Erez, & Johnson (2002), posit that one of the most determining factors of OCB is organizational commitment because apart from the fact that it motivates employees to remain with an organization, it also makes employees active members of the organization (Steyrer et al., 2008). Furthermore, it has been argued by Tsai, Cheng, and Chang (2010) that OCB among employees can develop if organizations are able to retain committed employees. In relation to this, results of a study carried out by Khan and Rashid (2012) revealed that commitment is significantly correlated with OCB. Findings of Liu and Cohen (2010) also showed that continuance commitment has a strong effect on OCB. In the same vein, a positive correlation between affective commitment and OCB was found by Allen et al. (2011). A recent study conducted by Premchandani and Sitlani (2015) among 375 employees working in various service organizations in Indore and nearby areas examined the relationship between organizational commitments and OCB with the aim of determining if affective, continuous and normative organizational commitment are strong determinants of OCB or not. The results of the analysis carried out using ‘Structural Equation Model’ (SEM) revealed that normative commitment had the strongest effect on OCB, followed by affective commitment and the weakest predictor of OCB was found to be continuous commitment.

2. Model Development

According to Baran, Shanock & Miller (2012), it is of great importance to study the factors that determine the relationship between employees and the organization which makes the employees feel supported by the organization (Baran, Shanock, & Miller, 2012). Organizational support researches are based on reciprocal specification as well as social exchange theory which makes employees feel obliged to the organization thereby performing better while being satisfied with their jobs (Chiu et al., 2015).

A review of literature has revealed the existence of inconsistency of findings on the effect of organizational support on OCB. Some examples of such studies are given here. Miao and Kim (2010), found a significant and positive effect of organizational support on OCB and job satisfaction. However, Ahmed et al., (2015) in their met-analysis on the outcomes of organizational support revealed that organizational support has a moderate impact on OCB. Chan (2014), found a weak and negative relationship exist between organizational support and OCB. Due to this inconsistencies, further studies were suggested by Ahmad and Omar (2015) so that the reasons behind the inconsistencies in findings on the impact of organizational support on OCB can be determined. The aim of this is to bridge the empirical gap identified in this area.

Numerous researchers have placed emphasis on the significant effect of organizational support on OCB (Allen, Evans, & White, 2011; Olowookere, 2014; Premchandani & Sitlani, 2015; Rehan & Islam, 2013; Steyrer et al., 2008). Job satisfaction of employees can be improved through organizational commitment while their willingness to be more involved in organizational citizenship behaviour increases (Paulin, Ferguson, & Bergeron, 2006). Yet, many studies have failed to prove that there is a significant and positive correlation

between organizational commitment and OCB (Chu et al., 2005; Tang & Ibrahim, 1998; Williams & Anderson, 1991). Inadequacy in specific and simultaneous studies about the association between foci and different dimensions of commitment and organizational citizenship behaviour has been found in the literature (Duarte, 2015). Therefore, it has been suggested by Dehghani et al., (2015) that further studies be conducted in order to determine the relationship between OCB and other variables such as organizational commitment. This study is carried out to examine organizational commitment as a determining factor of OCB based on the recommendations of other researchers, inadequate specific studies and result inconsistencies.

By examining the effect of organizational support and organizational commitment on OCB, this study seeks to identify and bridge the possible gaps that might have a consequence on the current study.

Figure 1.1: Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment as determinants of OCB.

3. Conclusion

Based on the review of literature on organizational commitment, organizational support and OCB there are inconsistencies regarding the findings of studies on the effect of organizational support on OCB. The current literature highlights organizational support and organizational commitment as factors that significantly influence OCB.

Organizational commitment is regarded as the belief which an employee has in the organization, the employee's desire to continue being a member of the organization and loyal. Findings of previous studies have found that high level of job satisfaction can determine organizational commitment which in turn drives the employees towards developing OCB. Through organizational support, the employees are assured of the willingness of the organization to support them and meet their socio-emotional needs. When the organization shows the employees support, then the employees will be motivated to be more committed to work in the interest of the organization. This denotes the social exchange theory; employees that perceive their organizations as supportive tend to put in more effort in helping the organization achieve its goals.

As a result of the rapid global change, organizations are working hard to learn as well as teach their employees organizational behaviour that will help the organization adapt and thrive successfully in the global competitive marketplace which is continually changing. In this regard, it is expected that employees go beyond their roles, job descriptions and duties to enhance the overall performance of the organization. Managers of organizations are in need of such employees who can go beyond their job boundaries to ensure that the performance of the organization is excellent. This kind behaviour of behaviour displayed by employees also gives room for the development of OCB.

Despite the fact that organizational support has been found to have strong effect on OCB than on in-role performance, not much empirical studies have been conducted on the relationship between organizational support and OCB. More so, organizational support has been found to be a predicting factor for OCB than role-required tasks. Previous researches have examined this relationship and have found that organizational support is positively related with OCB. So many researchers have placed emphasis on organizational commitment as a

significant determinant of OCB; their studies have found that organizational commitment is positively related to all dimensions of OCB. It can therefore be concluded that this study contributes to the literature on organizational commitment, organizational support and OCB. This study indicates that organizational commitment and organizational support are major determinants of citizenship behaviours. Thus, organizations should give priority to employee support as well as enhance their commitment to the organization which will in turn motivate them to be willing to perform extra roles outside their job descriptions in order to achieve the goals of the organization.

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